

mosaic

MOSAIC co-creation methodology toolkit

Section 4: Ideation.

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Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

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Table of Contents

1. Example of co-creation general timeline	3
2. Example of Idea definition canvas for participants	4
3. Example of Idea definition template for participants	5
4. Example of Idea definition facilitation guideline.....	6
5. Example of template for a narrative description of the idea(s) emerged	10
6. Example of Diary for participants / facilitators to record their impressions during the process	11
7. Example of Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) for the management of co-created ideas' property rights.....	12

1. Example of co-creation general timeline

Step 1: Define the prototype.

- What is the core value of our project?
- What questions do we have about our project?
- How can we represent our project?

Step 2: Build the prototype.

- Use resources to start building the prototype
- How does the building change the project?
- What new questions does this open?

Step 3: Define the experimentation protocol (and finish the prototype...).

- Who are our users? When and where should we find them?
- Which experience of the prototype and the project should we offer?
- What are our questions?
- How should we gather feedback?

Step 4: Experiment with the prototype and gather feedback (i.e. open doors event).

Step 5: Evaluate your project through the feedback.

- What did we learn from the users' feedback?
- What strengths and weaknesses of our project did this unveil? Are there unexpected opportunities? Unexpected risks?
- Which questions does it open for the future of our project?
- How could we improve our project? Should we adjust it or transform it completely?

Step 6: Improvement of the project, depending on the feedback and the group's progress.

- Articulate a new version of the project.
- Build a new prototype.
- Test with a different protocol.

2. Example of Idea definition canvas for participants

1. Basic objective.	2. Target.
3. Which information on air quality (which level of detail)?	4. Which Information on the Impact of Air Quality on Health?
1. Which indications for prevention?	2. How and/or where?
3. Value of the idea.	4. Other.

3. Example of Idea definition template for participants

The aim of today's meeting is for your group to agree on an idea and detail it as much as possible. Here is a template that might help you do this. Follow these simple steps.

First, individually try to remember the ideas that appeared in your cluster. You are also welcome to suggest new ideas that fit your cluster. Write them down on individual post-its.

Choosing the first idea: We have to choose one of the ideas (not necessarily your favourite). As a group choose one idea that makes the most of this group, that reflects the multiple perspectives you are all bringing with you. Each of you will now speak in turn: you have one minute to draw the group's attention towards one valuable idea OR one valuable element in this idea OR a new element that should be injected in the ideas. Have a discussion and try to agree on one idea. In case of disagreement, you can have a vote to decide the chosen idea.

Crafting the idea together: Each of you has now one opportunity to make the idea better, more precise, or simply to ensure that the idea is relevant for them. Each of you will speak in turn to modify one element of the idea:

- You can add an element.
- You can transform one element.
- You can give details about an aspect of the idea.
- You can raise awareness about a context, a constraint, something that has to be taken into account.

After everyone has spoken once, the idea may be quite different from the start... But this is now your common idea!

Detailing your idea: when you reached a consensus you may fill in the following template:

Who are the primary users of this? (don't answer everyone, rather choose the group who would benefit most from the idea)
How/when do they use it?
How does it make their life better?
What is special in this idea? Where is its core value?

4. Example of Idea definition facilitation guideline

0:00-0:10 – Welcome and introduction

Welcome to this new gathering and thanks for joining. My name is XXX and I will be your main facilitator today. Before we start, some housekeeping information:

- *(If food/drinks are available)* There is food available ..., please feel free to grab coffee, drinks or something to eat at any time. We have also foreseen a long break in the middle of the meeting for you to enjoy the food and get some fresh air.
- If needed, emergency exits are...
- Toilets are...
-

This meeting will be a follow-up from the Gathering. Today, we will agree on the precise idea on which the whole cluster will be working on. In the next weeks, we will use a process called prototyping to give shape to your project, articulate its details, and explore the opportunities it offers. We may even test it or dialogue around it with potential users and collect feedback. But this will come later!

For today, we will still focus on the ideas. We will bring back the ideas from last time and we may also explore new ones, but with one objective in mind: have everyone agree on one idea, on one common project. And we would like a bit more than the simple agreement of everyone: we would like the involvement of each of you in the idea, so that each of you bring their own perspective and experience to it.

0:10-0:15 – Icebreaker

Before we start speaking about the idea, let's wake up our bodies. I would like everyone to stand up. Now, I am going to ask you to scatter in the room as evenly as possible, so we have the best use of this space... *(Encourage them, draw their attention to empty spaces or people being to close...)*.

Today we will speak again about mobility, about moving in the city. Some of you live close to this very room. Some of you live further away. I will now give you precisely three minutes to organise yourselves and change places. The closer you live from here, the closer you should stand from this corner *(choose one corner of the room)*. The further you live, the closer you should be from this other corner *(show the opposite corner)*. You are allowed to speak, but NOT to use your phones, computers or other devices. No internet or GPS allowed! Ready? You have three minutes! *(Start the timer)*.

(After three minutes:) You probably had very different distances to go through, and used different means of transportation... Let's now use that diversity of experience for our ideas. Let's go back to our seats.

0:15-0:30 – Bringing back ideas

As you may remember, last time you were grouped by cluster. And from now on, we'll only be interested in your cluster's ideas. Do you remember the ideas to improve mobility that your cluster had identified last time? Let's take a few sticky notes and try to remember them.

We are going to write only one idea on each sticky note. First, each of you is going to do the exercise alone. Please write each idea that you remember, from this group only, from the Gathering. If new ideas came to your mind in last few days, or if a new idea is coming now,

you may add these as well – still each idea on a separate sticky note. Now, let’s gather all the sticky notes together, and spot what ideas we remember best, what ideas were almost forgotten, and what new ideas are emerging.

(Ask participants to tell an idea. Stick it on the board and ask if someone else had the same idea. Collect and group identical ideas. Underline any idea that was only remembered by a few, and if a similar idea is presented differently by several participants, stress the difference of perspective. Also collect the new ideas and add them on the board).

Some ideas may be more or less suited for this kind of project. Let’s see a few principles that may lead you to change some ideas or to add new ones. Do you find that some of the ideas on the board are not ambitious enough? Then, how can you suggest another version, more ambitious, that really changes the way we do things? Are some ideas too radical, or too ambitious? Do they seek to achieve something desirable but that seems utopic? Then, can you find ways to support the *change* towards that new utopic vision, rather than forcing the utopic vision immediately? Take a moment to look at the current ideas and suggest any new ones stemming in your mind from these reflections.

0:30-1:00 – Choosing the initial idea

Great, we have our bunch of ideas for this cluster! But now we need to work on one project for the whole group. This means that it will not be the idea of one of you, but an idea that is owned by everyone in this group – and thus shaped by everyone in this group.

It may be a bit uncomfortable, in many ways. If your favourite idea is here, it may not be chosen. If it is chosen, it will be modified by everyone here, so you may lose what you love most about it. However, the value of this kind of process is not only that we have a great project, but also that this project is grounded on a variety of perspectives, of experiences. The negotiation and the transformation of the idea by everyone is an essential element of the co-creation process, ensuring that we bring the whole complexity of this group into the idea.

First, let’s choose the initial idea we will be working on. I insist on the word “initial”, as this will merely be the first direction. Each of you is going to have 30 seconds to draw the group’s attention to one idea, or to one aspect of an idea, that you find valuable. Use your 30 seconds wisely: please do not respond to other participants’ views, just state your own views.

(Let each participant talk once only. If someone speaks 30 seconds, tell them that their time is up to bring them to a close.)

Thanks for this! Now, let’s have a quick vote to choose our initial direction. You can all vote for one idea only: which one will you choose? *(To mark the vote, invite the participants to use sticky dots or draw hearts with markers. If it is a tie or almost tie, make a second round of votes with the two finalists’ ideas).* This is now our initial idea. However, it still needs to be crafted by everyone here. But first of all, let’s take a well-deserved break!

01:00-01:05 – Break *(may be reduced to 5 minutes if needed).*

01:05-01:40 – Crafting the idea

We now need to ensure that each one – with their own experience of the world - is involved in it. I will ask each of you to find one way to make the idea better. This can be:

- An additional element you add to the idea,
- A transformation of a part of the idea,

- More details or better precision,
- A context or something we should be aware of and take into account.

If you don't like the initial idea so much, then the question is: what do we need to add or change so you are part of it? If you like the idea already, the question is: how can we make it more precise, more detailed, more relevant? Each of you can add one improvement, and one only! Take a first minute, in silence, to think about the improvement you may bring to make this idea clearer, more relevant to you, more helpful to others.

Now everyone, will state their improvement: listen carefully, as the other participants' improvements may also be an inspiration for you. *(Have a roundtable of improvements. Rephrase the idea regularly so participants keep track of its transformation. Unless there is a big issue, this is not a moment for debate: it's a moment to see how the idea evolves and grow into something for everyone. At the end of the roundtable, if some participants are vocal about not liking the idea anymore, you can ask them what they would need to change and try to adapt the idea to find a common ground).*

(Optional: if you bring Lego bricks, you may do the same exercise where the initial idea is represented by an initial simple construction of a few bricks. Whenever a participant transforms the idea, they have to add some bricks (and NOT remove any). This is a nice way to materialize the process, add a bit of creativity and give the feeling that we are looking for a coherent "whole" involving everyone).

01:40-01:55 Writing the idea together

We now have an idea that is truly reflecting this group! First of all, congratulations, this was not an easy task at all, and you succeeded! Secondly, we now have our project settled, so let's write it not to forget it.

Invite participants to fill in the two templates which you can find in this Toolkit: the "Template for idea definition and planning further work ("Idea card")" and the "Idea definition canvas" for participants. Mostly, draw their attention to the core value of the idea, what makes the idea "special" and different from existing services. It may be special for specific users only, or in specific contexts only. Depending on the time left, you may have participants draft answers for the first template only, or for both of them. If you still have time, you may invite them to start thinking about their team organisation, if they have specific roles, dates and times for meetings, tools (Emails, Google docs), etc.

01:55-02:00 Wrap-up

Thank you for your participation! We now have a clear view of our idea. The next steps will have us build a representation of that idea. Depending on the project, it may involve Lego bricks, the use of a Fab Lab to build a model, a storyboard to detail the way the idea is used, a movie that narrates the service... or other things, like the ones you see in the pictures of that slide. This will be decided together in the next meeting!

(Optional, only if you have enough time). Before we leave, I would like you to conclude this meeting with a few questions from you. No affirmation, no opinion, just an open question for all of us. We will not provide any answer, we will just leave each other with these questions. What question did that meeting open for you? What question may we share and reflect on? Whenever you want to, you can say your question. *(Questions are just said by participants, not written... Please note them for us.)*

Thank you, we will be in touch soon by email. We're very grateful for your time and we hope you enjoyed the activities. Have a nice evening and a safe travel home. Bye bye!

5. Example of template for a narrative description of the idea(s) emerged

For each idea describe the following:

- Participants
- The idea
- Objective(s) of the tool/product/service
- Target
- Benchmarking (*What is already there, if and how it differs from the group's proposal*)
- The proposed solution (*including sources of data and information and description of the tool/product/service - you can also insert pictures and describe them – and technologies used*)
- Messages to be conveyed

If not described elsewhere, please also include descriptions of:

- Strengths
- Potential further developments
- Unresolved issues
- Possible promotion activities
- Estimated development costs

6. Example of Diary for participants / facilitators to record their impressions during the process

DIARY OF THE DAY

This diary can be filled in during the meeting, or in the following days. The best is to fill it in through a shared document.

Photos

Did you keep some photos of the day? Add them here!

Diary

Please write a paragraph to answer each question. A different participant an answer each question, but please state your name at the end of your paragraph, to make visible the multiplicity of authors. Make your answers as personal as possible! This will be part of the archive of the process.

- What happened today? How did I feel about it?
- Was our project transformed by the activities today? What changed? What progressed?
- Do you remember a specific moment, event or anecdote from the session?

Questions sheet

- What does our idea need to be successful?
- What seems to be a critical element for the idea?
- How can we make it easy to use, simple and reliable?
- What could increase its impact, help more people, make it more efficient?
- How can we ensure people will actually use it?
- What part of the idea is likely to work well? Where will the issues most probably come from?
- Are there some ethical issues linked to the idea? Some social or political issues? Are there some acceptability issues?

7. Example of Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) for the management of co-created ideas' property rights

As a prerequisite for your participation in the (...) process, (...) intends to outline here below in a clear manner the expectations concerning the way in which those participating in the project should deal with information to which they may have access during meetings and group work within the project:

- (i) You are required to treat as strictly confidential any technical information you may have access to within the (...) process provided by any other participant and not to disclose it to third parties. This does not apply to information that:
 - (a) are, or will become, public knowledge.
 - (b) are already known.
 - (c) are or will become disclosed by third parties without this resulting in a breach of this Agreement.
 - (d) are or will be independently and autonomously developed by parties who had no knowledge of the Confidential Information. Any such Confidential Information obtained shall not be disseminated and must be kept secure and confidential.
- (ii) you are obliged to use the information provided solely for what you will be required within the scope of the (...) project and for no other purpose.
- (iii) you are obliged to use the information provided solely for what you will be required within the scope of the (...) project and for no other purpose. This Agreement shall be effective from (...) until (...). The obligation to maintain confidentiality shall remain in force until such time as the information in question enters the public domain, unless breached by you or any other participant in the (...) project, and in any case for a maximum of 3 years. In case of violation of these requests, the participant will be excluded from participating in of the process and from access to the materials of the process.

(...) commits to treat with the same confidentiality any information received from all participants in the (...) project.

Name and Surname - Signature (legible)

